

INVESTIGATIONS ON NICKEL AMMINES. PART II. PRECIPITATION
OF NICKELOUS HYDROXIDE UNDER DIFFERENT CONDITIONS
AND ITS SOLUBILITY IN AQUEOUS AMMONIA

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Observations on the solubility of nickelous hydroxide, prepared by using different proportions of nickel and hydroxyl ions, have been recorded. The difference in solubility of the different samples has been ascribed to the amphoteric nature of the hydroxide.

It is interesting to note that there is a wide variation in the observations of various workers regarding the solubility of hydrated nickelous oxide in aqueous ammonia solutions; workers like Bonsdroff (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, 41, 185) and Strack (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3840), while giving their observations, suggest that the variation and non-agreement in their results are due to the different modifications of the hydrated oxide employed by them. The existing literature, however, does not convey any conclusive explanation of the different modifications of nickelous hydroxide.

In our detailed study of the complex ammines of nickel (to be published later) it was considered necessary to investigate those varying conditions which lead to differences in the solubility of the nickelous hydroxide in aqueous ammonia. In this paper we have employed nickelous hydroxide prepared by using different proportions of nickelous salt and alkali, in order to elucidate the nature of the hydroxide obtained under different conditions, and its effect, on its solubility.

We have observed that nickelous hydroxide, precipitated from a soluble nickel salt by caustic soda, generally requires smaller quantities of the alkali for complete precipitation. In the cold about 12% less alkali is required than the theoretical quantity for complete removal of nickel from an $M/2$ solution, whereas in the hot a still smaller quantity is sufficient for complete precipitation. Similar observations have been recorded by Britton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2210). We have, however, noted that the amount of alkali needed, approaches the theoretical value for dilute nickel salt solutions. We find that the character of the hydroxide precipitated by deficient, equivalent, and a slight excess of caustic soda, in the cold, differs remarkably in its capacity to dissolve in aqueous ammonia. The solubility was found to be the least for samples obtained with increasing quantities of alkali. A similar phenomenon has been observed by Dey and Ghosh (this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 181) and Mehrotra and Ghosh (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1946, 15, 161) in the case of cupric hydroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three samples, A, B and C, of nickelous hydroxide precipitates were obtained by the interaction of a fixed volume of nickel sulphate with varying amounts of caustic soda solutions, as shown in the following table.

TABLE I

150 c.c. of $M/2$ -NiSO₄ solution $\equiv$ 138.7 c.c. of 1.082*N*-NaOH solution.
Temp. = 30°.

Sample.	Vol. of $M/2$ -NiSO ₄ .	Vol. of NaOH.	Remarks.
A	150 c.c.	118.7 c.c.	Alkali, 11.38% less
B	150	138.7	Alkali, equivalent
C	150	158.7	Alkali, 14.38% excess

The precipitation was carried out at a room temperature of 30°, with continuous stirring. The nickelous hydroxide formed was filtered and washed with cold distilled water till the filtrate was free from nickel, alkali and sulphate ions. The precipitates were then shaken vigorously with distilled water to make a homogeneous suspension, and the final volume raised to 500 c.c. Nickel content of the suspension was then estimated volumetrically using potassium cyanide (cf. Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II, p. 680), and several estimations from 10 c.c. of the suspension gave concordant results. The final volume of the three suspensions were so adjusted that the nickel content was the same in all the three cases. The sulphate in each of the finally diluted suspensions was then estimated and the following results were obtained.

TABLE II

Nickel in mg. atoms per litre = 98.65.

Sample.	Sulphate in mg. M ion per litre.
A	0.5059
B	0.5012
C	0.3857

The above table shows that the sulphate is associated with the precipitates and it decreases with increasing quantity of alkali employed for precipitation. These results are in agreement with those obtained by Dey and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) in the case of cupric hydroxide.

Solubility in Aqueous Ammonia Solutions.—Each of the suspensions (25 c.c.) containing the same amount of nickel was taken in glass stoppered Jena glass bottles and 50 c.c. of aqueous ammonia solutions of different concentrations were added, so that the final concentration of ammonia in each was 0.5*M*, 1.0*M*, 1.5*M*, 2.0*M*, 2.5*M* and 3.0*M* respectively. The suspensions with the aqueous ammonia were allowed to stand for approximately 18 to 20 hours at room temperature (30°) with occasional shaking, when the nickel content in the solution became constant. The suspensions were then filtered through a double layer of Whatman's No. 42 filter papers, and nickel was estimated in 25 c.c. of the filtrate. The following table gives the results.

TABLE III

Nickel in each suspension = 98.65 mg. atoms per litre.

Final conc. of ammonia soln.	Amount of nickel dissolved in mg. atoms per litre of suspension		
	A.	B.	C.
0.5M	0.3312	0.2473	0.1628
1.0	2.561	2.303	2.058
1.5	4.745	4.310	3.951
2.0	7.442	6.775	6.357
2.5	12.00	11.570	10.250
3.0	14.090	17.540	11.330

The above results show that the sample of nickelous hydroxide precipitated with excess of alkali is more soluble. It is also observed that the three types of precipitates show a variation in their physical properties, namely, the size of the particles, a slight variation in colour, ranging from olive green to whitish green, and the gelatinous nature of the precipitates. Thus the precipitates obtained with excess of alkali are more compact.

It was thought necessary to see the effect of the grain size of the particles of the hydroxide on its solubility in ammonia solutions. For this purpose nickelous hydroxide sample was obtained by precipitating the hydroxide with excess of alkali (14.4% more than the equivalent amount) at 80°, and an even suspension was obtained as described above and contained no free nickel or hydroxyl ions but only a small quantity of sulphate ion associated with the precipitate. This suspension was divided in two parts, P and Q. The portion Q was then thoroughly ground in an agate mortar, small amounts at a time, the whole operation lasting for about four hours. The volume of the suspensions was then raised to 200 c.c. each. Nickel in both the suspensions was the same, namely 86.62 mg. atoms/litre. The sulphate associated in each of the finally diluted suspensions was estimated and was found to be identical. The difference in the size of the particles of the suspensions was established by taking the two suspensions in two long tubes (1 cm. diameter) and noting the time taken by the suspensions to settle down through a fixed height, as noted below.

TABLE IV

Distance settled.	Time taken by		Distance settled.	Time taken by	
	P.	Q.		P.	Q.
1 cm.	51 mins.	20 mins.	20 cm.	105 mins.	140 mins.
2	33	45	25	130	175
3	60	80	30	170	222
15	85	115			

It is thus observed that the precipitate, which was ground, takes a longer time to settle, showing the particles of the precipitate in the suspension Q are smaller in size than those of the other.

The solubilities of these two types of precipitates in 0.5M, 1.0M and 1.5M aqueous ammonia solutions were determined by the method already described. The following results were obtained.

TABLE V

Nickel in each of the suspensions = 86.62 mg. atoms per litre.

Final conc. of ammonia.	Amount of dissolved Ni in mg. atoms per lit. of NH ₃ in suspension	
	P.	Q.
0.5 M	0.1614	0.1610
1.0	2.0530	2.0510
1.5	4.0780	4.0760

It is thus evident from the above table that reduction in the size of the particles has no remarkable effect on the solubility of the hydroxide in aqueous ammonia solution.

DISCUSSION

From the experimental results the solubility of the hydroxide samples precipitated with excess of alkali appears to be least soluble; whereas those with deficient alkali are more soluble, and further the solubility is more related to the chemical character rather than the grain size of the precipitated hydroxide.

Considering the amphoteric nature of nickelous hydroxide, we may consider the following reactions occurring on the surface of the hydroxide :

According to the above scheme, equation (i), nickelous hydroxide behaves as a base, and in equation (ii), H^+ ion is liberated. Naturally, if OH' ions are deficient in the system $\text{NiSO}_4\text{--NaOH}$, the equation (i) will proceed from left to right and thus anions like sulphate will be preferentially associated by the precipitate because of its basic character. If, however, OH' ions are in excess in the system, the equation (ii) will proceed from left to right and the hydroxide will show acidic properties, thus diminishing the chances of the adsorption of sulphate ions.

For the formation of amines the necessary electrons are supplied by the ammonia molecules. Each ammonia molecule donates two electrons. If, therefore, the nickelous hydroxide is converted, of course, partially into Ni(OH)^+ , the affinity for electrons will increase, and the tendency of the formation of an ammine will then be very prominent.

We are of the opinion that the solubility of nickelous hydroxide in ammonia, due to the formation of an ammine, first passes through a colloidal stage, and finally goes to complete dissolution forming complex ammino-nickel ion with increasing concentration of ammonia (cf. Dey, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1948, 3, 373; Ghosh and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 457; 1926, 30, 628). It is but apparent that an acid surface of Ni(OH)^+ , as represented by equation (ii), will be a favourable condition for the adsorption of ammonia to form a colloidal solution.

The quantity of sulphate associated with the precipitate varies with the amount of alkali used for precipitation, but the formation of the nickel ammine does not seem to be directly dependent on the amount of adsorbed sulphate. Thus, in Table III, we find that the variation in the solubility of nickelous hydroxide is considerable in samples A and B, though the difference in the amount of sulphate lies within 1%.

We thus conclude that for the favourable formation of complex nickel amines from hydrated nickelous oxide, the precipitate must be obtained with a lesser amount of alkali since excess of alkali gives a precipitate which is likely to be chemically less active and is thus unsuitable for co-ordination.

Further work on nickel amines is in progress, which will substantiate the view advanced in this paper and will form the subject matter of subsequent communications.